

Supporting Information

Passive Recording of Bioelectrical Signals from Non-Excitable Cells by Fluorescent Mirroring

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1. Fabrication of the nano-platform

The process flow is illustrated in **Supplementary Figure S1**. Silicon nitride (Si_3N_4) membranes with a thickness of 500 nm were fabricated on a silicon wafer (100) 535 μm thick, p-doped, and double side - coated (Si_3N_4 , Silicon Materials). Following membrane fabrication, individual $1.5 \times 1.5 \text{ mm}^2$ chips were obtained from the wafer by photolithography using the positive photoresist MICROPOSIT S1813, followed by Si_3N_4 Reactive Ion Etching (RIE – SENTECH SI500) using a mixtures of gases (CHF_3 and O_2 , 70 and 10 SCCM, 1 Pa, 20 °C, 30 W), and silicon wet etching in a potassium hydroxide solution (KOH 30 wt % for 8 hours). This process yielded individual silicon chips with a Si_3N_4 suspended membrane at the center. Nano-holes matrices were drilled across the membrane by Ga^+ focused ion beam (FIB, Helios NanoLab 650, 0.79 nA, 30 pC μm^{-2}), after depositing a conductive layer on the sample (5 nm of titanium and 20 nm of gold, e-beam evaporator Kurt J. Lesker PVD 75). Following this, 20 nm of gold were evaporated on the gold-coated side of the membrane in the same fashion, to cover the inside of the holes in preparation for galvanic electrodeposition. Gold electrochemical deposition was performed by immersing the sample into a bath of $\text{K}[\text{Au}(\text{CN})_2]$ dissolved in water (Parador HS – $[\text{Au}] = 3 \text{ g L}^{-1}$, pH = 4.2), and contacting the sample and a counter electrode to the negative and positive terminals of a current generator (35 mA, ~ 2V, 6 min, 35° C). This process yielded a ~ 1 μm thick gold layer on the deposition side, and 3D nano-electrodes on the opposite side of the membrane, grown in correspondence of each hole. The planar side of the membrane was then processed by photolithography and wet etching to define the working and

reference planar electrodes on the optical chamber. Photolithography materials and instruments included a primer solution to promote resist adhesion (H.M.D.S. TECHNIC) and a negative photoresist (MicroChemicals AZ5214), both spin-coated (4000 rpm for 60 s for both the primer and the photoresist) and baked at 112 °C for 1 min. Mask alignment (SÜSS MicroTec Mask Aligner—hard contact mode, exposure time = 8 s) to the chip was enabled by bespoke markers patterned during the previous photolithography step. After UV exposure, the photoresist underwent a post-exposure bake at 120 °C for 2 min, followed by another UV light exposure for 30 s. The sample was developed for 45 s (MicroChemicals AZ5214 Developer) and rinsed in water. Prior to gold wet etching (Merck, gold etchant standard, 45 s), the 3D microelectrodes on the concave side of the membrane were preserved by depositing S1813 photoresist (95 °C, 10 min). The samples were then cleaned in acetone, IPA, deionized water, and oxygen plasma treatment (300 s, 100 W, 100% O₂). A 3 nm thin film of SiO₂ was further deposited as a passivation layer by atomic layer deposition (ALD FlexAL) on the planar side of the membrane. A Plexiglas ring with internal diameter 8 mm, wall thickness 2 mm, and height 8 mm was glued on the top side of the sample by using PDMS (Sylgard 184, Dow Corning, 90 °C for 2 hours). Cells were cultivated inside the plexiglass ring, in contact with the 3D microelectrodes. The counter electrodes were fabricated by depositing 100 nm of ITO (RF Ar sputtering, Kenosistec Sputter Coater KS500 Confocal, 80 W, 50 SCCM (Ar flow), 0.5 SCCM (O₂ flow), room temperature) and 20 nm of gold (e-beam evaporation, as previously) on squared substrates of fused silica. The fluorophore dispersion was obtained by dissolving rhodamine 6G (Merck) in ethylene glycol (Merck) to obtain a final concentration of 0.2 mg mL⁻¹.

Supplementary Figure S1. Schematics of the fabrication process. A) Starting sample: double side – coated silicon wafer. B) Photolithography and dry etching to i) define the areas of chips and membranes, ii) etch away silicon nitride in the same areas to prepare the wafer for wet Si etching. C) Wet etching of silicon in KOH. Silicon chips with a centrally suspended Si_3N_4 membrane are obtained and further diced manually. From now on, chips are processed individually. D) Top, bottom, and sectional views of a single chip. Looking from top, a concave structure is observed, with the membrane at the bottom (this is the side where Si_3N_4 first and Silicon secondly, were etched). Flipping the chip, the membrane is seen lying on the same plane as the chip. By looking through a section of the chip, the suspended membrane is visible. An etching angle lower than 90° is observable due to the anisotropy of silicon wet etch in KOH. The chip is turned upside down to process the membrane on the on-plane side. E) Thermal evaporation of a Ti adhesion layer (5 nm) and Au (20 nm) to prepare the chip for focused ion beam (FIB) processing. In this step, a matrix of nano-holes is patterned such to cover the entire membrane. Further, another layer of Au (20 nm) is deposited to coat the inside of the holes prior to electrodeposition. F) Galvanic electrodeposition of gold allows to obtain 3D microstructures on the concave side of the membrane in correspondence of the holes. The top side remains

with a 1 μm layer of electro-deposited gold. G) The on-plane side of the membrane is patterned to obtain planar electrodes (each featuring a central working electrode and a surrounding hollow squared reference electrode), such that each covers a matrix of 5x5 3D microelectrodes on the bottom side. H) A SiO_2 layer (3 nm) is deposited as a to provide passivation. The chip is further cleaned in Piranha solution to remove contaminants as well as the titanium layer. I) A glass cylinder is bonded to the top side of the chip (concave membrane) using PDMS. Cells are cultivated on the membrane inside the cylinder such to contact the 3D microelectrodes. Recording is performed from the planar electrodes at the bottom.

Supplementary Figure S2. Examples of additional geometries fabricated within this work. The smallest size was designed such as to have a central square electrode with dimension $d = 10 \mu\text{m}$ and a pitch $p = 40 \mu\text{m}$. In this case, the central electrode was connected to four 3D electrodes on the top chamber.

2. Tox-FREE software

2.1. Experimental Data Format. The Tox-FREE software was specifically built to analyze the data resulting from this work and its future implementations. The program receives a video recording of the planar electrodes under fluorescence emission as an input, it recognizes the electrodes pairs, and plots the fluorescence intensity in the working and reference electrodes. It

allows to simultaneously analyze the whole electrodes matrix. The main data collected during the experiments consist of two images (**Supplementary Figure S2**), namely the electrode matrix imaged under white light illumination, where cells adhering to the electrodes are visible, and the electrode matrix imaged under fluorescence emission by stimulation at 532 nm, where the grayscale represents the intensity of the emitted light (i.e., the electrical signal coming from the 3D microelectrodes in the biological chamber).

Supplementary Figure S3. Micrographs of the typical acquired data. A) Electrodes matrix imaged under white light illumination. It is possible to discriminate the presence/absence of a cell or cell cluster on the electrodes. B) Electrodes matrix imaged under fluorescence stimulation at 532 nm. By correlating this image to the one in A, one can plot the fluorescence intensity variation observed between working and reference electrode pairs with or without cells.

2.2. Data Processing and Analysis. By clicking the *Open button* and selecting the desired file (.tif in the case of a video or .json if the file was previously created with the tox-FREE experimenter when recording in Binary format), the software takes a fluorescence image/video as an input (**Supplementary Figure S3**). After the file is loaded, the slider is used to navigate through it. The

Autoscale checkbox optimizes the visuals of the image by linearly scaling the data to the range 0 – 255, such that the pixel with minimum intensity is displayed as pure black and the one with maximum intensity is displayed as pure white. This is a merely visual effect and does not change the analysis.

Supplementary Figure S4. Opening window of the Tox-FREE software and Autoscale checkbox function.

The *Settings button* in the *Sensor Detection menu* allows to select and configure an appropriate detection method. This procedure was designed to be flexibly adaptable to different shapes and sizes of the electrodes, and be ready to be updated for future applications. In this case, we use the *Pattern Recognition* method to find templates of the electrodes shape within the image, taking into account both the working and the reference electrodes. The *Detect button* is used to identify the electrodes areas in the image. Following this, the *Surround checkbox* identifies the surrounding electrodes (i.e., the reference electrodes). By default, working electrodes are shown in white after sensor detection, and their reference electrodes are displayed in red. Following detection, the electrode pairs of interest can be selected by dragging an area on the image with the mouse, and

selected pads are highlighted with a green circle. The *Analyze button* is further used to extract the electrodes activity over time.

Supplementary Figure S5. Operation of the Tox-FREE software. Once the image is loaded, electrode pairs are detected by clicking the “Detect” button, and visualized by checking the “Sensors” and “Surround” boxes. The desired electrodes to measure can be selected by dragging a rectangle with the mouse, and they are highlighted in the software by green circles. The selected electrodes can be analyzed by clicking on the “Analyze” button, and “View Results” button to display the graphs. In this case, going back to the input image in Figure S4 and as shown in the inset image-at the bottom right under white light illumination, we can observe that the plot shows larger fluorescence shifts for the

electrodes in contact with cells, compared to the bare electrode. The toolbar below the graph allows to modify the visuals and export the associated data.

This only analyzes the first image of the loaded file to provide a quick first impression. The *Analyze All button* analyzes all images of the loaded recording, which can be individually observed by moving the cursor on the horizontal line placed at the top of the window. The *View Results button* is then used to open the analysis window and view the graph, which can be modified by using the upper and lower toolbars to change the visuals, export it as an image or export the data in Excel format.

2.3. Logic of the “Pattern recognition” algorithm. This paragraph explains more in detail the logic of the Pattern Recognition algorithm used by the software to identify the electrode pairs. The software first constructs a template for the ideal electrode shape, then convolves this template with the image and finds the points in the image having the best match to the template. The template matching procedure performs the following steps: (i) applies a median blur to the image with kernel size 5; (ii) applies a 3x3 sharpen kernel to the image; (iii) convolves the image with the sensor template; (iv) extracts the local maxima in the convolution result; (v) converts the picture to 8 bits if necessary; (vi) goes through all the local maxima and for each extracts the local area around it. Each local area corresponds to one electrode pair.

Sensor Area Detection. For each extracted local area, the algorithm goes through the following steps to determine the pixels corresponding to the electrodes and reference areas: (i) computes an automated threshold with the Otsu method; (ii) applies an Opening operator and then a Closing operator, both with kernel size 3 and 2 iterations to clean up the results; (iii) extracts the connected components of the thresholded image; (iv) assigns all pixels in the connected component

containing the center pixel to the electrode area (working electrodes); (v) assigns all pixels in connected components outside of the center to the reference area (reference electrodes).

Electrodes activity. The electrodes activity is computed as the mean intensity of their area. If the image contrast is reasonably good, the algorithm forms a rough square over the working electrode area. The surround area (reference electrode) is computed by: (i) constructing an outer area by enlarging the working electrode area by 8 pixels in all directions; (ii) constructing an inner area by enlarging the working electrode area by 2 pixels in all directions; (iii) subtracting the inner from the outer area. This results in a ring around the sensor; (iv) computing the activity of the reference electrodes as the mean activity in the surround area.

3. Finite element modeling

We used the COMSOL Multiphysics® software to define the surface charge density [1]. The model combines the transport of diluted species and electrostatics physics interfaces to account for mass and charge transfer [2]. The model contains 1D configuration below:

Supplementary Figure S6. 1D configuration model, where AC is the cell consisting of intracellular fluid AB and cell membrane BC [3], CD is the Au electrode and DF is the fluid consisting of rhodamine fluorophores diluted in ethylene glycol.

The following parameters were used in the model:

Table 1. Simulation parameters.

Parameter	Part of configuration model	Value
permittivity of intracellular fluid	<i>AB</i>	80
permittivity of cell membrane	<i>BC</i>	5
permittivity of Au electrode	<i>CD</i>	1
permittivity of fluid	<i>DF</i>	41.4
length of intracellular fluid	<i>AB</i>	3 μm
length of cell membrane	<i>BC</i>	2 μm
length of Au electrode	<i>CD</i>	1 μm
length of fluid	<i>DF</i>	0.5 μm
bulk concentration of rhodamine fluorophores	<i>DF</i>	0.2mg/mL
charge of cations	<i>DF</i>	+1
charge of anions	<i>DF</i>	-1

Electric potential (V_{cell}) was applied at point *A* in the range from 0 to -50 mV with a step of -10 mV. The surface charge density was calculated at Au-fluid interface (point *D*) using the equation below:

$$\sigma = -\frac{\varepsilon\phi_{\Delta}}{\lambda_{\text{S}}}$$

where ε is the permittivity of the fluid, ϕ_d is the difference between the applied electric potential (V_{cell}) and electric potential in point D , and λ_s is the Stern layer thickness (0.5nm in our case).

References:

[1] COMSOL Multiphysics® v. 6.0 www.comsol.com. COMSOL AB, Stockholm, Sweden.

[2] Diffuse double layer guide (application ID: 21981), <https://www.comsol.com/model/diffuse-double-layer-21981>

[3] S. Li, X. Chen, and F. Han, “Simulation of cell dielectric properties based on COMSOL”, JRNAL 4(4), 2018.